

A necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of Euclidean knight's tours on $2 \times 2 \times \cdots \times 2$ chessboards

Marco Ripà

Abstract: In Theorem 4.1 of [Ripà, M. (2024), Proving the existence of Euclidean knight's tours on $n \times n \times \cdots \times n$ chessboards for $n < 4$, Notes on Number Theory and Discrete Mathematics, 30(1), pp. 20–33], the author provided closed Euclidean knight's tours for every $2 \times 2 \times \cdots \times 2$ chessboard having at least 2^7 vertices, while no Euclidean knight's tour can exist on $C(2, k) := \{0, 1\}^k$ for $k < 6$. In the present note, we show closed Euclidean knight's tours on $C(2, 6)$ to prove a general statement that extends the mentioned Theorem 4.1 since Euclidean knight's tours exist on $C(2, k)$ if and only if $k \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

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1 Introduction

The Euclidean Knight's Tour problem asks to find a Hamiltonian path for the Euclidean knight [4] on a given set of points in the (k -dimensional) space \mathbb{E}^k so that the Euclidean knight can visit exactly once every vertex of the mentioned set.

Then, let us indicate by $C(2, k) := \underbrace{\{0, 1\} \times \{0, 1\} \times \cdots \times \{0, 1\}}_{k\text{-times}}$ each $2 \times 2 \times \cdots \times 2$ chessboard.

Accordingly, a Euclidean knight's tour on $C(2, k)$ is a sequence of $2^k - 1$ knight jumps of Euclidean length $\sqrt{5}$ chessboard units each (where one chessboard unit corresponds to the distance between the centers of adjacent squares of the chessboard) that let the knight visit exactly once all the 2^k corners of the k -cube $[0, 1]^k$.

Furthermore, if the ending vertex of $C(2, k)$, where the (Euclidean) knight stands after $2^k - 1$ jumps, is at a distance of $\sqrt{5}$ chessboard units from the starting position, we can perform the (2^k) -th move returning home, and we define the described cycle a *closed* (Euclidean) knight's tour.

2 An improved theorem

We introduce the following lemma to fill the $k = 6$ gap left by Theorem 4.1 of Reference [4].

Lemma 2.1. *Closed Euclidean knight's tours exist on $\{0, 1\}^6$.*

Proof. We constructively prove Lemma 2.1 by providing a valid sequence of 64 jumps of length $\sqrt{5}$ that a Euclidean knight can perform out of the $2^{6-1} \cdot 6$ edges describing the regular graph of legal knight moves on a 6-cube (i.e., the Euclidean knight's graph for $C(2, 6)$). The requested path is $P_c(2, 6) := (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1) \rightarrow (0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$ and it is a closed knight's tour since the Euclidean distance between $(0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$ and $(0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$ equals $\sqrt{(0-0)^2 + (1-0)^2 + (1-0)^2 + (1-0)^2 + (1-0)^2 + (1-0)^2}$.

Since $P_c(2, 6)$ describes a closed knight's tour on $C(2, 6)$ that we can reverse, mirror, and so forth, we get many other valid closed Euclidean knight's tours that join all the 64 corners of our 6-cube (furthermore, the existence of a lot of non-isomorphic closed knight's tours for $\{0, 1\}^6$ is assured by the sixth term of the OEIS sequence A066037 [3] which gives the exact number of cyclic 6-bit *Gray codes* [5]). \square

Now, we are ready to restate Theorem 4.1 of Reference [4] in a more complete form.

Theorem 2.1. *A Euclidean knight's tour exists on $C(2, k)$ if and only if $k \geq 6$. Furthermore, if there is a Euclidean knight's tour on a given $C(2, k)$, then closed Euclidean knight's tours exist for the same chessboard.*

Proof. We invoke Theorem 4.1 by Reference [4] together with Lemma 2.1 to state that there exist closed Euclidean knight's tours on $C(2, k)$ for each $k \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

Then, we conclude the proof by observing that no more than one (Euclidean) knight's move is possible on any $C(2, k)$ such that $k < 6$ since the maximum distance between two vertices of a k -cube corresponds to the distance between opposite pairs of corners, which is always equal to \sqrt{k} .

Hence, k cannot be smaller than 5 to allow (at least) one knight move on $C(2, k)$ and, given $k = 5$, the only jump that a Euclidean knight can perform is from a corner to the opposite corner of the same k -cube (and there is no turning back from there due to the Hamiltonian path constraint).

Therefore, $C(2, k)$ admits closed Euclidean knight's tours if and only if $k \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ (and there are at least 35838213722570883870720 of them, for any given $k \geq 6$, by Reference [3]). \square

3 Conclusion

Since the Euclidean knight move rule is consistent with the FIDE knight definition, provided by Article 3.6 of Reference [2], it generalizes the planar knight to higher dimensions, allowing the special move that changes 5 coordinates at once starting from $k = 5$.

Consequently, any known "classic" (possibly closed) knight's tour is also a Euclidean knight's tour, but the vice versa is not true since Theorem 2.1 provides Euclidean knight's tours for each $C(2, k)$ such that $k \geq 6$.

Then, given any k -tuple of positive integers (n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) satisfying $n_1 \leq n_2 \leq \dots \leq n_k$, the present knight definition lets us ask which other $n_1 \times n_2 \times \dots \times n_k$ chessboard configurations, that were previously forbidden by Theorem 3 of Reference [1], can be exploited in order to find new closed (Euclidean) knight's tours.

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References

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